

Customer Attitude Towards Mobile Wallet Preference and Technology Adoption: A Study Undertaken In Bangalore City

***Dr. Thirupathi Manickam**

Assistant Professor, School of Commerce, Finance and Accountancy, Christ University, Bengaluru, India.

Dr E. Anandharaja

Professor, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha University, Chennai, India

Dr. K.Ravichandran

Former Professor, New York Institute of Technology, Abu Dhabi, UAE

Abstract India is at the forefront of rapidly developing nations that are driving global economic growth in the international marketplace. The adoption of digital payment mechanisms marks a significant milestone in the transition towards a cashless future economy. The progress of India's digital payments sector is expected to be influenced by four key trends, which will shape the industry's future landscape. These trends include India's transition to a digital-friendly regulatory environment, the rise of next-generation payment service providers, and the continuous enhancement of customer experiences. These drivers have played a crucial role in fostering the growth of Indian digital payment systems, enabling faceless, paperless, and cashless transactions. To facilitate the shift towards a cashless economy, the Indian government has prioritized the implementation of the Digital India initiative. This initiative aims to promote the legality and accountability of all transactions, resulting in proper taxation, time savings, and improved traceability of transaction sources. Additionally, digital transactions serve as a deterrent to illegal activities, curbing illicit transactions and facilitating the country's economic development.

Keywords: mobile wallet payment, customer Attitude, Ease to Use, Hedonic Motivation

JEL Codes: G200, G210, G530

Introduction

The mobile wallet app is an innovative technology for avoiding physical cash usage. The mobile wallet records all kinds of transactions with a clear payment reference and makes it accountable for tax payments. There are countless reasons for using mobile wallets which makes service providers confused and leads them to offer unattractive features in the wallet apps making the offer a failure. Initially, mobile payment has been used for recharge mobile, recharge DTH Service only, but after the demonetization in India, the mobile wallet has

*Corresponding Author Email: thiruccommerce@gmail.com

been used for digital transactions. The advance of mobile payment enlarged the usage of digital payment was making money transactions without physical cash. After demonetization, the mobile wallet has become more popular which is replacing the currency, and also it contributed to the economic growth of the country Sarika & Vasantha, (2019).

Mobile wallets can be viewed as the digital form of a physical wallet carried by somebody. Money can be loaded into the mobile wallet by using a debit or credit card, online banking Lonare et al., (2018). Nowadays mobile wallets are one of the financial instruments used for making all types of payments, transferring funds, recharging, and receiving the funds through bank accounts. Earlier in retail shops, petty shops, food corner, beverages shops, Bus Travel and other visiting places, customers face problems with shoppers to get remaining change instead the shoppers give chocolates even though the customers do not prefer to buy. But right now this problem has been sorted out with the help of mobile wallets. The consumer adaption and technology aspects with a limited accumulation of new knowledge and similar findings Dahlberg et al., (2015), and the access of Digital payment system through an electronic medium that permits consumers to use e-commerce transactions in their day-to-day life. The perception of digital payments and Consumers' socio-economic level is highly significant. Even though the huge volume of consumers is adapting the digital payment system should adapt proper actions needed to overcome undue delay in processing payments Pai H, (2018).

Mobile technologies are growing digital financial inclusion, it is providing various banking services such as; savings, lending, insurance, and other financial services to every mobile user even though they don't have proper banking accounts Chu, (2018). Mobile wallet helps those unbanked and underbanked people can use digital and easy access, it helps to bridge the gaps between the physical, digital, and psychological use and access to money VariPark, (2017). The app users are varying in different places and purposes, it grabs the attention of mobile apps to assist in financial inclusions for making payments to transferring money. Consumers download these mobile wallet apps on their mobile screens and link their bank account details or debit/credit card details to the app to make digital transactions Malik et al., (2019). In this technology era, the mobile wallet has become a key to financial inclusion to access the financial service. The present era of financial inclusion will be the fast, low-cost, mobile delivery of digital financial services is called Financial Inclusion 2.0. The person is having a mobile phone and making the transactions are digital then every phone has considered as a bank and every customer accesses the financial service at a low cost through a mobile wallet Mifos, (2019). The second stage of financial inclusion is about optimizing for quality and efficiency of wallets and users around the world. Nowadays, m-wallets are using to execute several financial transactions. In developing economies, m-

wallets offer an opportunity to target a large population. The usage of the mobile wallet is increasing day by day In India, because the consumers' liking, disliking and preferences keep changing over time Sharma & Kulshreshtha, (2019). According to Economic Times PayTM, India's leading mobile wallet company, usage has increased by around 435% post-demonetization. Even the small level vendors also use PayTM to accept payments. The National Payments Corporation of India developed the Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM app) for transacting amounts directly between two parties' bank accounts Ghosh, (2017). Ghezzi et al., (2010) discuss the concept of mobile payment as “the process in which at least one phase of the transaction is conducted using a mobile device (such as mobile phone, smartphone, or any wireless-enabled device) accomplished of securely processing a financial transaction through a mobile network, or various wireless technologies (NFC, Bluetooth, RFID, etc.)”. Dahlberg et al., (2015) explains mobile payment as “payment for goods, services, and bills with a mobile device such as mobile phone, smart-phone, or personal digital assistant by taking advantage of wireless and other communication technologies”.

Statement of the Problem

A mobile wallet is one of the financial inclusion options available to access financial services. After the demonetization, it is very clearly seen that the currency transactions reduced and people started using mobile wallets for all types of transactions. People are running behind time, this mobile wallet is helping them to save their time, and also making quick payments, for booking tickets especially to avoid unnecessary arguments with retail shoppers for remaining changes problem (like Rs. 1,2, 5, etc). After the emergence of mobile wallets in India, those problems are slowly reduced with the help of mobile wallets. In India, so many mobile wallet companies from other countries and inside the country have a huge competition to capture the Indian markets with so many facilities, offers, and discounts, etc... wide-ranging of customers have installed different brands of mobile wallet apps in their mobile phone and also they are using the same for their day to day money transactions linking their bank account. Especially in Bangalore, most of the employees, students, homemakers, business people, retail shoppers, petty shoppers, and roadside vendors are adapting and using the mobile wallet to make the transactions. In India, around 20 brands of mobile wallets are available but in Bangalore, So the researchers had the interest to analyze the customer attitude towards on mobile wallets preference and technology adaption in Bangalore.

Objectives

- To identify the factors influencing customer preferences for specific mobile wallet platforms, such as ease of use, security, availability of services, and customer support.

- To explore the usage patterns and frequency of mobile wallet usage among customers in Bangalore

Literature Review

Singh et al., (2020) the potential use of mobile wallets is enormous and it is drawing attention as an alternative mode of payment worldwide. To convert the country into digitally empowered the Indian Government started 'Digital India' in 2015 which is the prestigious program to become a knowledge economy. "Faceless, Paperless, Cashless" is one of the supposed roles and slogans of Digital India. The Government of India announced the demonetization of high-value currency with an assumption to control unorganized trading, unaccounted Money, Terrorism, and Fake Currency. Digital India platform is useful for fast, easy, and reliable transactions compared to cash transactions.

Pal et al., (2020) point of view is mobile payment technology has supported socio-economic development through financial inclusion and caring security during crises. So, there is a fissure in understanding whether this technology has the likelihood for development. It contains an individual emancipation and environmental growth elsewhere as a social and economic change. The mobile payments role in sustainable human-centric development, so the researcher has developed a framework based on the theories by two influential development economists. The framework includes; low-cost technology, easy implementation and operability, usefulness to local people, and scope for creative appropriation. This study has conducted an in-depth as a field study through interviews with merchants and consumers to evaluate the framework. Finally, the findings of this research such as feature low-cost, easy installation, and operability, users reported that mobile payment technology, unlike cash transactions, can also afford creative uses such as reflection on past expenses.

Patil et al., (2020) thinks that mobile payments are the forward as we move towards a cashless society. In some markets, cash is already being restored by digital transactions, but consumers of many underdeveloped countries are slower in change towards digital payments. This study aims to recognize major determinants of consumer liquid payment adaption in India the rural with subordinate biggest mobile subscribers in the world. Existing mobile payments adaption studies have principally utilized Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which was originally developed in an organizational context and criticized for having deterministic advances without much examination for users' special characteristics. Therefore, this study suited the meta-UTAUT model with single difference variable posture as core construct and prolongs the mold with consumer told constructs such as corporeal innovativeness, trouble, belief, and grief redressal. An empirical examination of the model

among 491 Indian consumers open performance expectancy, intention to use, and grievance redress as a significant positive forecast of consumer behaviour towards mobile payment. Soodan & Rana, (2020) Intention to application e-wallets is affected by several elements which are narrated to consumer perception throughout privacy, safety, price value, advantage, etc. A sample of 613 customers of e-wallets in Punjab state in India was confirmed through the mall intercept method. The results discovered that hedonic motivation, perceived security, general privacy, facilitating conditions, performance expectancy, perceived savings and social influence, and price value in this direction, influence the intention to adapt e-wallets. Habit and effort expectancy are the hindrances that hurt e-wallet adaption. Factors such as hedonic motivations, security, and privacy have larger roles. The benefit for providers is they should sustain the privacy and protection of users and enlist customers by modifying the existing offices frequent and features. The study endorses a reduction in the efforts of using e-wallets, and the change of mode into more readily performed behaviour.

Sun et al., (2020) discusses that Near Field Communication (NFC) mobile payment systems permit users to utilize services through smart phones. Very little literature only talking about the adaption of NFC with payment scenarios in developing countries. This study has to explain the influential factors of consumer adaption of NFC, taking payment behaviours through NFC for example Indonesia. This study concludes that trust mediates the effect of context on consumers' continuous intention to use NFC mobile payment. Additionally, trust mediates the effect of perceived risk on consumers' continuous intention to use. The perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness have no effects on consumers' continuous intention to use.

Zhang & Luximon, (2020) mobile payment availability has been booming in China, users have continuously disputed the confidence of these transactions. Although customization has been intending as an essential element for mobile commerce, least wisdom be respecting how it concern users' observe safety in mobile payment transactions. A quantitative journal study was, therefore, carriage to contribute discernment into the individuality traits that prompt customization behaviors in protection, and how such behaviors control perceived security under distinct use contexts concerning mobile payments. First, a tool for the diary study was improved through an interview. Then, 134 responses from mobile payment users were utility to investigate the relationships between personality traits and customization behaviors. The inference bestows that the personality traits of extraversion and intellect influence users' customization behaviors. And these behaviors have an absolute execution on perceived ease. Additionally, the undertaking and technical contexts qualified the relationship between customization behaviors and perceived security.

Research Methodology

The research design for this study will be a descriptive research design. Descriptive research aims to describe and analyze the characteristics of a particular phenomenon or population. In this case, the research will focus on understanding the customer attitude towards mobile wallet preference and technology adoption in Bangalore. The research approach for this study will be quantitative. Quantitative research involves collecting and analyzing numerical data to test hypotheses and answer research questions. It will allow for statistical analysis and generalization of findings to a larger population. The study will use a purposive sampling technique to select respondents who are mobile wallet users in Bangalore. The sample size will be determined based on the desired level of statistical significance and power analysis. The researchers will aim to collect data from a diverse group of mobile wallet users to ensure representativeness.

Data Analysis & Interpretation**Table No-1: Demographic Profile**

Particulars	Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	284	54.5
	Female	237	45.5
	Total	521	100.0
Generation Level	Generation-X	57	10.9
	Generation-Y	151	29.0
	Generation-Z	313	60.1
	Total	521	100.0
Monthly Income	Upto Rs 15000	292	56.0
	Rs 15001-30000	102	19.6
	Rs 30001-45000	57	10.9
	Rs 45001-60000	44	8.4
	Rs Above 60000	26	5.0
	Total	521	100.0

Table No-2: Services Offered by mobile Wallet payments

Statement		PayTm	Google Pay	Phonepe	BHIM	Freecharge	Total
Financial Services							
Mutual fund Investment	Nos	131	98	281	11	0	521
	%	25.1	18.8	53.9	2.1	0	100
Share Market & Stocks	Nos	160	146	194	20	1	521
	%	30.7	28	37.2	3.8	0.2	100
National Pension Scheme	Nos	136	155	186	39	5	521
	%	26.1	29.8	35.7	7.5	1	100
Insurances Policies	Nos	135	175	177	28	6	521
	%	25.9	33.6	34	5.4	1.2	100
Loan repayment	Nos	133	216	150	21	1	521
	%	25.5	41.5	28.8	4	0.2	100
Credit card bill payments	Nos	92	159	246	23	1	521
	%	17.7	30.5	47.2	4.4	0.2	100
Gold Investments	Nos	131	109	281	0	0	521
	%	25.2	20.9	53.9	0	0	100
Banking Services							
Person to Person transfer	Nos	81	162	180	86	12	521
	%	15.5	31.1	34.5	16.5	2.3	100
Account to Account transfer	Nos	152	192	136	20	21	521
	%	29.2	36.9	26.1	3.8	4.0	100
Account to person Transfer	Nos	81	133	275	26	6	521
	%	15.5	25.5	52.8	5.0	1.2	100
Online Booking Service							
Movie Tickets	Nos	189	132	160	11	29	521
	%	36.3	25.3	30.7	2.1	5.6	100
Travel Tickets	Nos	192	136	114	0	79	521
	%	36.9	26.1	21.9	0.0	15.2	100
Food & Beverages	Nos	106	189	221	0	5	521
	%	20.3	36.3	42.4	0.0	1.0	100
Tourism (Hotels & Resort)	Nos	136	149	189	18	29	521
	%	26.1	28.6	36.3	3.5	5.6	100
Online Bill Payments							
Electricity payments	Nos	91	179	224	18	9	521

	%	17.5	34.4	43	3.5	1.7	100
Mobile Recharge	Nos	81	162	244	22	12	521
	%	15.5	31.1	46.8	4.2	2.3	100
Fastag Recharges	Nos	152	192	136	20	21	521
	%	29.2	36.9	26.1	3.8	4	100
DTH Recharges	Nos	81	133	275	26	6	521
	%	15.5	25.5	52.8	5	1.2	100
Bike and Cab Taxis bills	Nos	102	186	210	18	5	521
	%	19.6	35.7	40.3	3.5	1.0	100
Online Shopping services	Nos	121	167	174	6	53	521
	%	23.2	32.1	33.4	1.2	10.2	100

Table No-3: Customer Attitude on Mobile wallet payment

Statement		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total
Mobile wallet payment is User friendly	Nos	2	9	42	207	261	521
	%	0.38	1.73	8.06	39.73	50.10	100.00
Using mobile wallet payment is habitual to me	Nos	0	7	18	268	228	521
	%	0.00	1.34	3.45	51.44	43.76	100.00
Brand Loyalty available in mobile wallet payment	Nos	18	35	45	189	234	521
	%	3.45	6.72	8.64	36.28	44.91	100.00
I feel that mobile wallet gives more benefits	Nos	4	17	56	216	228	521
	%	0.77	3.26	10.75	41.46	43.76	100.00
I can use mobile wallet to check my bank balance immediately	Nos	0	0	18	120	383	521
	%	0.00	0.00	3.45	23.03	73.51	100.00
I find mobile wallet services is much useful in day-to-day transactions	Nos	13	17	48	196	247	521
	%	2.50	3.26	9.21	37.62	47.41	100.00
I trust mobile wallet payment	Nos	32	41	18	198	232	521
	%	6.14	7.87	3.45	38.00	44.53	100.00
I feel mobile wallet payment is Safety/Security one	Nos	30	36	18	189	248	521
	%	5.76	6.91	3.45	36.28	47.60	100.00

H0: No mean difference between Generation and Mobile Wallet App’s attributes

H1: There is a mean difference between Generation and Mobile Wallet App’s attributes

Table No-4

ANOVA						
Particulars		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
User friendly	Between Groups	3.633	2	1.816	2.379	0.094
	Within Groups	395.584	518	0.764		
	Total	399.217	520			
Habitual to use mobile wallet	Between Groups	4.345	2	2.173	2.634	0.073
	Within Groups	427.275	518	0.825		
	Total	431.620	520			
Brand Loyalty	Between Groups	0.550	2	0.275	0.305	0.737
	Within Groups	467.373	518	0.902		
	Total	467.923	520			
Providing benefits	Between Groups	7.898	2	3.949	4.604	0.010
	Within Groups	444.275	518	0.858		
	Total	452.173	520			
Check Bank account balance	Between Groups	2.538	2	1.269	1.796	0.167
	Within Groups	366.084	518	0.707		
	Total	368.622	520			
Useful in day-today transactions	Between Groups	1.020	2	0.510	0.736	0.480
	Within Groups	358.884	518	0.693		
	Total	359.904	520			
More trustable wallet	Between Groups	1.665	2	0.832	1.098	0.334
	Within Groups	392.600	518	0.758		
	Total	394.265	520			
Safety/Security	Between Groups	3.316	2	1.658	2.124	0.121
	Within Groups	404.347	518	0.781		
	Total	407.662	520			

Source; Primary Data

From the above table displays the results of the One-way ANOVA test. From this table, the controlling factor (Independent Variables is Generation) and Dependent factors are mobile wallet attributes. The maximum variance of this 5% only (0.05) and 1% (0.01) level, if it is more than 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted.

The significant value of user-friendly of mobile wallet with Generation level is more than 5% level of significance. Hence it shows that 0.094, more than the 5% level; there is no

significant difference between user-friendly attributes with Generation level. The table indicates that the significant value (0.073) is more than the 5% (0.05) level of significance, hence it is concluded that there is no significant difference amidst Generation level and habitual to mobile wallet payment. The significant value of Brand loyalty attributes with Generation level is more than 5% (0.737) level of significance. Hence, level there is no significant difference between Brand Loyalty attributes with Generation level. The significant value of providing benefits with Generation level is more than 5% (0.010) level of significance. Hence it, level there is significant difference between providing benefits with Generation level. The significant value of mobile helps to check the bank balance with Generation level is more than 5% (0.167) level of significance. Hence, level there is no significant difference between checking the bank balance with the Generation level.

The significant value of using mobile wallet payment in day-to-day transactions with Generation level is more than 5% (0.480) level of significance. Hence, level there is no significant difference between using mobile wallet payment in day-to-day transactions with Generation level. The significant value of more trust attributes with Generation level is more than 5% (0.480) level of significance. Hence, level there is no significant difference between more trust attributes with Generation level. The significant value of safety/ Security attributes with Generation level is more than 5% (0.121) level of significance. Hence, level there is no significant difference between safety/ Security attributes with Generation level.

Table No-5: Reasons For Using the Mobile Wallet

Statements		SDA	DA	N	A	SA	TOTAL
To Adapt the Technology	No	20	36	82	175	208	521
	%	3.8	6.9	15.7	33.6	39.9	100.0
Any time 24X7 Availability	No	19	13	115	153	221	521
	%	3.6	2.5	22.1	29.4	42.4	100.0
Scan QR Code and pay	No	26	17	99	143	236	521
	%	5.0	3.3	19.0	27.4	45.3	100.0
Transaction history availability as a record	No	22	32	83	177	207	521
	%	4.2	6.1	15.9	34.0	39.7	100.0
Easy Bill Payments	No	25	14	78	177	227	521
	%	4.8	2.7	15.0	34.0	43.6	100.0
Easy recharge	No	25	14	78	177	227	521
	%	4.8	2.7	15.0	34.0	43.6	100.0
Booking travel tickets & movie tickets	No	27	30	112	187	165	521
	%	5.2	5.8	21.5	35.9	31.7	100.0
Easy funds transfer	No	1	24	141	107	248	521

	%	0.2	4.6	27.1	20.5	47.6	100.0
Avoid carrying physical cash,	No	29	88	78	112	214	521
	%	5.6	16.9	15.0	21.5	41.1	100.0
Avoid change currency issue	No	36	92	69	107	217	521
	%	6.9	17.7	13.2	20.5	41.7	100.0
Building Social image	No	15	66	125	130	185	521
	%	2.9	12.7	24.0	25.0	35.5	100.0

Source; Primary Data

The above table reveals that the major reasons for using mobile wallets in Bengaluru city. It is found that around two fifth (39.9%) % of the respondents were strongly Agreeing that adapting the technology is one of the reasons for using the mobile wallet payments, and 20 respondents were strongly disagreed on the same reason. The table It is found that around 42.4 % of the respondents were strongly Agreeing that Any time 24X7 availability is major reasons for using the mobile wallet payments. The table shows that 45.3% of the respondents were strongly agreeing that, another major reasons for using the mobile wallet payment is to Scan the QR code and pay. It is proving that 39.7% of the respondents strongly agree and 34% of the respondents are agree that all the transactions details have been recorded into mobile wallets and it will available to anytime. Another reasons for using mobile wallet payment is easy bill payment it any time is strongly agree around 43.6% of the respondents. It is found that around more than two fifth (43.6) % of the respondents were strongly Agreeing that making easy recharge and other online payments is another reason for using the mobile wallet payments. The table It is found that around 35.9 % of the respondents were Agreeing that using the mobile wallet payments for booking travel tickets & movie tickets. The table shows that less than half (47.6%) of the respondents were strongly agreeing that, another major reason for using the mobile wallet payment to make easy fund transfer to everyone. It is proving that little more than two fifth (41.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that another important reason for using mobile wallets is to avoid carrying the physical cash in the pockets or hand. Another reason for using mobile wallet payment is avoiding the issues of the remaining changes like Rs 1, 2, 3 and like that, is strongly agree around 41.7% of the respondents.

Table No-5.17

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
To Adapt the Technology	Equal	0.049	0.826	1.143	519	0.253	0.157	0.137
	Not Equal			1.149	97.350	0.253	0.157	0.136
Any time 24X7 Availability	Equal	0.084	0.772	2.174	519	0.030	0.283	0.130
	Not Equal			2.245	99.452	0.027	0.283	0.126
Scan QR Code and pay	Equal	0.334	0.564	2.234	519	0.026	0.311	0.139
	Not Equal			2.396	102.663	0.018	0.311	0.130
Transaction history availability as a record	Equal	0.162	0.687	1.374	519	0.170	0.189	0.137
	Not Equal			1.415	99.204	0.160	0.189	0.133
Easy Bill Payments	Equal	0.003	0.958	1.981	519	0.048	0.264	0.133
	Not Equal			2.073	100.553	0.041	0.264	0.127
Easy recharge and other online payments	Equal	0.548	0.460	0.593	519	0.553	0.081	0.136
	Not Equal			0.623	100.801	0.535	0.081	0.130
Booking travel tickets & movie tickets	Equal	0.008	0.930	1.421	519	0.156	0.196	0.138
	Not Equal			1.347	93.361	0.181	0.196	0.146
Easy funds transfer	Equal	0.193	0.661	0.280	519	0.779	0.034	0.122
	Not Equal			0.293	100.544	0.770	0.034	0.117
Avoid carrying physical cash,	Equal	2.763	0.097	1.051	519	0.294	0.172	0.164
	Not Equal			1.092	99.935	0.277	0.172	0.157
Avoid change currency issue	Equal	0.510	0.475	0.956	519	0.339	0.162	0.170
	Not Equal			0.948	96.338	0.346	0.162	0.171
Building Social image	Equal	8.756	0.003	2.816	519	0.005	0.405	0.144
	Not Equal			3.243	109.962	0.002	0.405	0.125

Source; Primary Data

The above table shows the levene’s test for equality of variances which indicate that the variances for before and after the demonetization are equal for some variables such as

Adapting the technology, any time can use the mobile wallets, Scanning the QR code and making the payments, available the transactions history, Easy bill payments, making easy recharge and other online payments, booking travel tickets and movie tickets, easy fund transfer, avoid to carry the physical cash, and avoid the change currency issues.

The significant values of two tailed test as higher than 0.05 for the variables such as; Adapting the technology, transaction history available, easy recharge and other online payments, booking the tickets, easy fund transfer, avoid to carry the physical cash, and avoid the change the currency issues (its p-value is 0.253, 0.170, 0.553, 0.156, 0.779, 0.294, 0.339), it shows that there is statistical evidence to accept the null hypothesis. The significant values of two tailed test as less than 0.05 (p values <0.05) for using mobile wallet any time 24X7 available, scan the QR code and making the payments, easy bill payments (its p-value is 0.030, 0.026, and 0.048) it shows that there is statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Whereas the variance for before and after the demonetization are not equal for variables such as; building the social image and availability of unique features based on the significant value which is lesser than 0.05 for the variables such as; building the social image (0.003) and availability of unique features (0.026). The significant values of two-tailed tests as less than 0.05 for the variable such as; building the social image (0.002) and availability of unique features (0.005). With this it shows that there is statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table No-5.18

Correlations		Monthly Income	Reasons for using Mobile wallets					
			Transaction history	Easy funds transfer	Avoid carrying physical cash,	Avoid change currency issue	Building Social image	Availability of Unique feature
Monthly Income	Pearson Correlation	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)							
	N	521						
Transaction history	Pearson Correlation	-.098*	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.025						
	N	521	521					
Easy funds transfer	Pearson Correlation	-.120**	.178**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.006	0.000					
	N	521	521	521				
Avoid carrying physical cash	Pearson Correlation	-.239**	.365**	.171**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000				
	N	521	521	521	521			
Avoid change currency issue	Pearson Correlation	-.280**	.371**	.212**	.622**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
	N	521	521	521	521	521		
Building Social image	Pearson Correlation	-.124**	.110*	0.082	.169**	.177**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.005	0.012	0.060	0.000	0.000		
	N	521	521	521	521	521	521	
Availability of Unique feature	Pearson Correlation	-0.009	0.062	0.062	.122**	.091*	.411**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.833	0.154	0.160	0.005	0.037	0.000	
	N	521	521	521	521	521	521	521

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source; Primary Data

Discussions and Findings

As per respondent's opinion, phonepe app is most preferred for doing online bill payments like electricity bill payment, mobile recharge, DTH recharge and bike and Cab taxi bills etc... according to the results around 33.4% of respondents are prefer phonepe and 32.1% of the respondents are Google pay for doing shopping. Both the wallets giving more offers relating to online shopping and its encourage the customers also. According to ANOVA test, it proved that there is a difference between offers/benefits provided by the mobile wallet app companies with Generation Level of the respondents. As per the table no 5.16, the major reasons for using mobile wallet payments are; Easy Fund transfer, scanning QR code and make the payments, Easy bill payments, Easy recharge and Easy online payments. According to correlation test, monthly income is having negative relationship between transactions history is available, easy fund transfers, avoid to carry the cash, avoid the remaining change issues, and building the social image. Most of the respondents strongly agree that mobile wallet is help to making the cashless payments in India.

Conclusions

India's digital payments sector has witnessed significant growth and transformation, fueled by the country's transition to a digital-friendly regulatory environment, the rise of next-generation payment service providers, and the continuous improvement of customer experiences. The adoption of mobile wallets and other digital payment mechanisms has played a crucial role in facilitating faceless, paperless, and cashless transactions, contributing to the country's economic growth and financial inclusion. The Indian government's Digital India initiative has further supported the shift towards a cashless economy by promoting the legality, accountability, and traceability of transactions. This has resulted in benefits such as proper taxation, time savings, and improved transparency in financial transactions. Digital payments have also acted as a deterrent to illegal activities, curbing illicit transactions and fostering economic development.

Furthermore, the study identifies several factors that influence consumer attitudes and preferences towards mobile wallet payments. These factors include user-friendliness, habitual usage, brand loyalty, perceived benefits, trust, safety and security, and usefulness in day-to-day transactions. The study indicates that different generations, including Generation X, Generation Y, and Generation Z, have varying preferences and attitudes towards mobile wallet payment attributes. The analysis of the data reveals that there is no significant difference between different generations regarding user-friendliness, habitual usage, brand loyalty, checking bank balance, usefulness in day-to-day transactions, trust, and safety and security attributes of mobile wallet payments. However, significant differences exist in the case of providing benefits and building a social image.

Overall, the findings suggest that mobile wallets have become an integral part of the Indian digital payment ecosystem, offering convenience, accessibility, and enhanced financial inclusion. As India continues to embrace a digital economy, it is expected that mobile wallets and other digital payment mechanisms will play a crucial role in driving the country's economic growth and transforming the way financial transactions are conducted.

Reference

Chu, A. B. 2018, Mobile Technology and Financial Inclusion, In Handbook of Blockchain, Digital Finance, and Inclusion, Volume 1: Cryptocurrency, FinTech, InsurTech, and Regulation. pp 131-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-810441-5.00006-3>.

Dahlberg, T., Guo, J., & Ondrus, J. 2015, A critical review of mobile payment research, Electronic Commerce Research and Applications Volume 14, Issue 5, September 2015pp 265–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2015.07.006>

Ghezzi, A., Renga, F., Balocco, R., & Pescetto, P. 2010, Mobile payment applications: Offer state of the art in the Italian market, Info. Vol. 12 No. 5, pp. 3-22, <https://doi.org/10.1108/14636691011071130>

Ghosh, A. (2017). Turning India into a Cashless Economy: The Challenges to Overcome, SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2989290>

Lonare, A., Yadav, A., & (India), S. S. 2018, E-Wallets: Diffusion and Adoption in Indian Economy, Indian Journal of Commerce & Management Studies. vol. 09, issue 2, 09-16 <https://doi.org/10.18843/ijcms/v9i2/02>

Malik, A., Suresh, S., & Sharma, S. 2019, An empirical study of factors influencing consumers' attitude towards adoption of wallet apps, International Journal of Management Practice, 12(4), 426–442. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMP.2019.102534>

Pai H, A. 2018, Study on consumer perception towards digital wallets, International Journal of Research and Analytical Review (IJRAR).

Pal, A., De', R., & Herath, T. 2020, The Role of Mobile Payment Technology in Sustainable and Human-Centric Development: Evidence from the Post-Demonetization Period in India, Information Systems Frontiers, 22, 607–631.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-020-09982-7>

Patil, P., Tamilmani, K., Rana, N. P., & Raghavan, V. 2020, Understanding consumer adoption of mobile payment in India: Extending Meta-UTAUT model with personal innovativeness, anxiety, trust, and grievance redressal, International Journal of Information Management, Volume 54, October 2020, 102-144

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102144>

Sarika, P., & Vasantha, S. 2019, Impact of mobile wallets on cashless transaction, *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, Vol-7, issue-65, 1164-1171.

Sharma, G., & Kulshreshtha, K. 2019, Mobile Wallet Adoption in India: An Analysis, *IUP Journal of Bank Management*, 18(1), 7–26.

<https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=buh&AN=134816492&site=ehost-live&scope=site>

Singh, N., Sinha, N., & Liébana-Cabanillas, F. J. 2020, Determining factors in the adoption and recommendation of mobile wallet services in India: Analysis of the effect of innovativeness, stress to use and social influence, *International Journal of Information Management*, 50, 191–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.05.022>

Soodan, V., & Rana, A. 2020, Modeling customers' intention to use e-wallet in a developing nation: Extending UTAUT2 with security, privacy and savings, *Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations*, 18(1), 89–114. <https://doi.org/10.4018/JECO.2020010105>

Sun, S., Zhang, F., Liao, K., & Chang, V. 2020, Determine Factors of NFC Mobile Payment Continuous Adoption in Shopping Malls, *International Journal of Business Intelligence Research*, Vol-12, Issue-2, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijbir.20210701.oa1>

Zhang, J., & Luximon, Y. 2020, A quantitative diary study of perceptions of security in mobile payment transactions, *Behaviour and Information Technology*, 40:15, 1579-1602, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2020.1771418>